

DEVELOPMENT OF ENDURANCE IN STUDENTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES AT A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract. *This article will discuss the role of developing students' endurance in physical education classes. The importance of developing endurance and the basic provisions that allow for competent training to develop it will be considered.*

Keywords: *physical culture; endurance; exercises, psychological.*

INTRODUCTION

Physical culture is one of the most important elements in the life of every person. Today it is no longer possible to imagine our life without sports. Most people simply like to watch sports competitions, cheer for athletes, rejoice at their victories and experience defeats with them. But, unfortunately, not everyone engages in physical education on their own every day, at least at the level of morning exercises. People cannot fully understand that sport, joining the flow of their life, can not only change its course somewhat, but also have a beneficial effect on the state of health, not only physical, but also psychological. After all, it's no secret that physical activity reduces stress levels, bringing psychological functions to a stable state. Health implies complete physical, spiritual and social well-being.[9]

Relevance: As a result of recent studies, there has been a significant deterioration in the physical fitness and overall health of students studying in higher education institutions. According to scientific research, about half of high school students and schoolchildren have chronic diseases. Quite often, students suffer from diseases of the musculoskeletal and cardiovascular systems, which are caused by a lack of physical activity among students, nutrition, unfavorable environmental conditions and modern lifestyle. About 40% of boys and girls entering universities have 2-3 chronic diseases, and only about 15% of applicants can be considered practically healthy. According to statistics, about 1 million children graduating from school are completely exempt from physical education, and more than 2.5 million graduates have never been involved in sports sections. And only about 60% of young men can be drafted into the armed forces for health reasons. Over the past thirty years, the number of citizens fit for military service has decreased from 92 to 58%. More than 40% of school graduates, as well as students of secondary specialized and higher educational institutions, are not able to meet the lowest standards for physical fitness. The reduction of sports infrastructures, the lack of sports and recreation complexes, the lack of sports clubs, the lack of specialists in the field of physical education has led in recent years to a decrease in physical activity among schoolchildren and students, as well as to the development of chronic diseases, to huge physical defects and to a deterioration in physical fitness modern youth. Physical education in higher educational institutions is carried out mainly according to a standard program, i.e. according to the classical form of training organization. Increasingly, we see different approaches to developing physical qualities in students. Therefore, being in a constant search for more effective ways to develop physical qualities, it can be assumed that not all possibilities have been realized. Scientists have been studying the manifestation, development and education of general endurance for a long time. However, we have not found any scientific and methodological

work carried out on students of higher educational institutions (institutes, universities, academies, etc.) over the past two decades in the public domain. Although the degree of its manifestation in physical education lessons, in our opinion, is quite large. In this regard, there is a need for an in-depth study of the development of general endurance among university students in physical education classes and sports sections.

The entire modern system of physical education in educational institutions has long been in need of a radical restructuring aimed at ensuring a high-quality level of physical education and physical fitness of students. In our opinion, one of the priority areas in the activities of educational institutions should be the creation of optimal conditions for increasing the physical activity of students, holding physical education and recreational and sectional sports events at various levels. And in the future, involving students in participating in the Universiade and Spartakiads. Particularly relevant is the implementation of the physical culture and sports complex “Alpomish and Barchinoy”, aimed at increasing the general level of knowledge of the population about the means and forms of organizing independent physical education classes.

In the modern world, the system of physical education in a higher educational institution requires improvement in all its components, including methods of providing education, determining the direction and correct placement of value guidelines, as well as the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies. This is primarily due to the tendency towards a decline in the level of health among students, characterized by an insufficient level of physical fitness and, above all, endurance. A low level of student endurance limits obtaining excellent results in classes, and, accordingly, the general physical condition of students. Most students are not able to fully perform exercises related to endurance. That is why the development of this quality in physical education classes is relevant at the present time.

To solve the problem of reducing the level of physical fitness of students, as well as to introduce young people to a healthy lifestyle, it was proposed to introduce new methods from the field of fitness, which are currently the most popular among young people.

Physical culture is an academic discipline in a higher educational institution and represents the most important component in the formation of the holistic development of a student's personality. Physical culture affects all important aspects of an individual that are transmitted genetically; they develop in the process of life under the influence of upbringing, activity and the environment.

Purpose: To study the role of developing endurance in students during physical education classes at a higher educational institution.

Speaking about the scientific novelty of the proposed article, it should be said about the importance of physical training and, in particular, developed endurance in future specialists. The modern state is increasingly paying attention to the level of health of the population and the development of its physical qualities, respectively. Every year new methods and means appear to maintain a high level of physical fitness of young specialists, which provokes the continuous development of the field of physical education. Modern production requires not only a qualified specialist, but also a person with good physical fitness and health.

RESULTS

First, we need to define the concept of “endurance.” Turning to the dictionary of terms in physical education, we get the following definitions:

1) endurance is the ability to perform work of moderate intensity for a long time with the global functioning of the muscular system;

2) endurance is a person's ability to perform work of a non-specific nature for a long time, which has a positive effect on the development of specific components of a person's performance.[4]

Based on these definitions and practical indicators, the development of endurance significantly increases the level of increase in physical performance, which is most important for students taking a course in physical education.

So, let's look at which exercises are most suitable for developing students' endurance in physical education classes. According to research, the best method for developing endurance is cyclic aerobic exercise, among which running is the most accessible for all students. With a clear dosage of load and rest intervals, as well as a combination of these exercises with athletics and outdoor games, you can achieve significant results in the development of endurance and general physical fitness in general. You should do these exercises in combination, as this increases the effectiveness of these methods, and the effect achieved during exercise in this way lasts longer than when performing these exercises separately.

Let's look at the general effects that regular endurance exercises have on a student's body. First of all, adaptive mechanisms are improved and a person's nervous tension is relieved. Metabolic processes in the body and blood supply also improve.[2] All these effects have a positive impact on a person's general condition, including well-being and performance. The fact is that during training, the volume of circulating blood increases, which is due to an increase in plasma content in the blood, thereby reducing the load on the heart. With proper exercise, the level of endurance increases rapidly, which leads to the achievement of goals in physical development.[1] In addition to improving the general physical condition of students when working on endurance, there is also an improvement in performance in activities not related to physical education. There is a significant reduction in fatigue, cessation of headaches and improvement in reaction time.[3] This is due to improved brain function, since with improved blood circulation, oxygen supply to it and other organs of the human body improves.

When conducting a physical education lesson, the teacher, giving exercises to develop endurance, must take into account the individual characteristics of each student's body and correctly distribute the load for each student in order to avoid overwork. Only in this case, as well as with regular training, endurance exercises will give the desired result. It is also important to engage in motivational work with students; the teacher should conduct a lecture on the benefits of these exercises and their effectiveness. In the absence of students' dedication in physical education classes, the effectiveness of endurance exercises tends to zero, and the likelihood of fainting and accidents increases, since the student has no idea about the correct execution of the complex. This is, first of all, a violation of safety regulations.[5]

Thus, for more effective development of general endurance among university students, it is necessary to use "circuit training" in physical education classes. Today, in order to maintain health, it is necessary to work to prevent an increase in physical activity not only in physical education classes, but also in everyday life, as well as monitor nutrition and daily routine, and ultimately create a healthy lifestyle. These serious tasks are set directly for all educational institutions, and in connection with the adoption of new documents by the Ministry of Health and Social Development, new opportunities are opening up.

CONCLUSION

We can come to the general conclusion that the development of endurance in physical education classes plays an important role in the overall complex of physical education. By improving his endurance, thanks to the correct loads and methods determined by the teacher, the student improves his health, physical and mental. Physical education classes in a higher

educational institution stimulate the improvement of public health and, consequently, the improvement of the performance of future specialists, which is important for modern production.

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